

“Teachers’ Job Effectiveness and Students’ Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria”

Dr.N. A.Ishaq; B. I. Zaifada; H. A. Apeh
Faculty of Education, University of Abuja

Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between teachers’ job effectiveness and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. Two research questions and one null hypothesis guided the study. The population comprised 312 public senior secondary schools and 312 principals, from which a sample of 62 schools and 62 principals was selected using a multistage sampling procedure. Two researcher-developed instruments, titled Teachers’ Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ) and Students’ Academic Performance Proforma (SAPP), were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and content validation, after which a pilot test was conducted. The reliability index of the TJEQ was established at 0.79 using the split-half method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Mean scores, standard deviation, and percentages were used to answer the research questions, while multiple regression analysis was employed to test the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed a high level of teachers’ job effectiveness and a generally good performance in students’ SSCE results from 2014 to 2023, despite observable fluctuations over the ten-year period. The study concluded that teachers’ job effectiveness is a significant predictor of students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. Consequently, it was recommended, among others, that school principals should provide targeted training opportunities to enhance teachers’ effectiveness in lesson planning and delivery, classroom management, student assessment, and the use of appropriate teaching

methods. In addition, school principals, in collaboration with the Nasarawa State Teaching Service Commission, should invest in continuous professional development programmes and create an enabling environment that supports active teacher participation.

Keywords:

Teachers’ job effectiveness; students’ academic performance; public senior secondary schools; SSCE; Nasarawa State.

Introduction

Teachers occupy a pivotal position in the Nigerian education system, particularly at the secondary school level where learners acquire the academic foundations required for higher education and meaningful societal participation. As primary agents of instruction, teachers are responsible for translating educational policies and curricula into classroom practices that shape students’ learning experiences and outcomes. Empirical studies have consistently established that teachers exert a substantial influence on students’ educational development and academic achievement (Kotherja, 2013). In recognition of this central role, international education bodies have identified teachers as one of the most critical determinants of education quality and learning outcomes globally (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2018). Consequently, the effectiveness with which teachers perform their professional responsibilities remains a key factor in students’ academic success (Bourn, Hunt, & Bamber, 2017).

Within the school system, teachers' job effectiveness has emerged as a crucial construct for understanding variations in students' academic performance. Teachers' job effectiveness refers to the extent to which teachers competently execute instructional duties in ways that facilitate meaningful learning and the attainment of educational objectives. It encompasses observable professional behaviours that directly influence classroom processes and learning outcomes. According to Arogundade, Fakunle, and Olofin (2021), teachers' job effectiveness reflects teachers' capacity to achieve instructional goals as prescribed by educational authorities and stakeholders. Similarly, Osifila (2020) conceptualised teachers' job effectiveness as the degree of teachers' commitment to instructional delivery, ethical conduct, and the pursuit of improved academic performance among students.

More specifically, teachers' job effectiveness manifests through several interrelated dimensions that collectively shape instructional quality. In this study, four dimensions are emphasised: effectiveness in lesson planning and delivery, classroom management, students' assessment and feedback, and the use of diversified teaching methods. Lesson planning and delivery provide the structural and pedagogical framework for classroom instruction, outlining instructional objectives, teaching strategies, learning activities, and evaluation procedures necessary for achieving intended learning outcomes (English Club, 2014). Closely related to this is classroom management, which involves the organisation and regulation of students, instructional materials, and the learning environment to ensure orderly and productive learning experiences (Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019).

In addition, effective assessment and feedback practices enable teachers to monitor students' learning progress, identify learning gaps, and make informed instructional adjustments that support academic improvement. Assessment serves not only as a measure of learning outcomes but also as a tool for enhancing instructional effectiveness when accompanied by constructive feedback. Furthermore, the selection and application of appropriate teaching methods play a critical role in facilitating

students' understanding of subject matter. Teaching methods refer to the strategies and approaches employed by teachers to present content in ways that accommodate learners' abilities and promote active engagement, comprehension, and academic achievement (Olowo & Fashiku, 2019).

Against this backdrop, students' academic performance remains a major concern for education stakeholders at the secondary school level, given its implications for individual educational progression and national development. Academic performance is commonly assessed through students' results in internal school assessments and external standardised examinations such as the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE). As noted by Olowo and Fashiku (2019), students' academic performance represents the measurable outcomes of learning as reflected in examination scores and certification results within the school system.

However, available evidence suggests a persistent pattern of underperformance among secondary school students in public examinations. Reports from the West African Examinations Council (WAEC Records, 2012–2021) indicate that between 2012 and 2021, only 57.26% of candidates who sat for the WASSCE obtained a minimum of five credit passes, including English Language and Mathematics. This implies that a substantial proportion of candidates—approximately 42.74%—failed to meet the basic requirements for admission into tertiary institutions.

This challenge is particularly evident in Nasarawa State. WAEC result statistics from 2014 to 2021 reveal a mean performance percentage of 38.62%, indicating that less than half of the candidates attained the minimum benchmark of five credit passes, including English Language and Mathematics. The consistently low performance of students in public examinations in the state raises critical concerns about the effectiveness of instructional practices in public senior secondary schools.

Given the central role of teachers in the teaching–learning process, the declining trend in students' academic performance in Nasarawa State necessitates a focused examination of

teacher-related variables that may account for this outcome. Teachers' job effectiveness, as reflected in their instructional practices and classroom behaviours, constitutes a plausible explanatory factor. While previous studies have examined aspects of teacher effectiveness and student achievement, empirical evidence on the predictive relationship between specific dimensions of teachers' job effectiveness and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State remains limited. Consequently, this study seeks to fill this gap by empirically examining teachers' job effectiveness as a predictor of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State has remained persistently low, particularly in external examinations. Evidence from the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's reports indicates that between 2014 and 2021, only 38.62% of candidates who sat for the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nasarawa State obtained the minimum requirement of five credit passes, including English Language and Mathematics. This outcome reflects a failure rate of 61.38% within the period (WAEC Result Statistics, SSCE 2014–2021). Furthermore, performance rankings during these years consistently placed Nasarawa State outside the top ten performing states among the thirty-six states of the federation, underscoring the severity of the academic performance challenge.

Beyond examination statistics, observations within public senior secondary schools in the state suggest concerns regarding the effectiveness with which some teachers discharge their instructional responsibilities. Reports from school administrators and education stakeholders indicate that certain teachers demonstrate limitations in key areas of professional practice, including mastery of subject content, effective lesson planning and delivery, classroom management, student assessment and record keeping, as well as the provision of instructional leadership during the teaching–learning process. These aspects are

central indicators of teachers' job effectiveness and are directly linked to students' learning experiences and academic outcomes.

The persistent underperformance of students in public examinations, coupled with perceived inadequacies in teachers' job effectiveness, has raised critical questions regarding the extent to which teachers' instructional practices influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. Although teachers are widely acknowledged as pivotal determinants of students' academic success, empirical evidence establishing the nature and strength of the relationship between teachers' job effectiveness and students' academic performance within the state remains limited.

In view of these concerns, there is a compelling need for an empirical investigation into teachers' job effectiveness and its relationship with students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. This study therefore seeks to address this gap by examining whether teachers' job effectiveness significantly predicts students' academic performance in the state.

Objectives of the Study

- i. Ascertain the level of teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.
- ii. Establish the trend in students' academic performance in SSCE results in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria from 2014 to 2023.
- iii. Determine the relationship between teachers' job effectiveness and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the level of teachers' job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria?
2. What is the trend in students' academic performance in SSCE results in public senior

secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria from 2014 to 2023?

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' job effectiveness and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Teaching is a dedicated academic endeavour and a critical component of the educational process and for this reason the teaching effectiveness of teachers is imperative in order to achieve sustainable educational goals and objectives. Various researchers in education have made attempts at conceptualizing teachers' job effectiveness due to its importance to the actualization of predetermined instructional objectives across diverse subject areas and eventually satisfactory academic outcomes among students.

According to Arop, Ekpang and Owam (2018), teachers' job effectiveness refers to the degree at which teachers are discharging their pedagogical duties in the school which has the capacity to support or pull down the school from reaching its goals. Arogundade, Fakunle and Olofin (2021) opined that teachers' effectiveness is the ability of teachers to achieve goals and objectives set for them by the constituted authorities of the ministries of education and other education stakeholders. Dash and Barman (2016) posited that teachers' job effectiveness is the collection of characteristics, competencies and behaviour of teachers at all educational levels that enable students to reach desired outcome. This implies that teachers' job effectiveness is key to ensuring academic excellence among students in secondary schools. Furthermore, Osifila (2020) described teachers' job effectiveness as the extent to which teachers are dedicated to instructional delivery and display moral uprightness and academic performance in the teaching profession. In a related manner, Oviawe (2016) noted that teachers' job effectiveness is the ability of the

teacher to employ appropriate techniques and strategies to impart on the learners' knowledge, skills and competencies required to bring about desired positive learning outcomes.

In this study, teachers' job effectiveness refers to the capability of teaching staff to prepare and deliver instructional plans; assess students' performance and provide feedback, maintain classroom rules; and diversify their use of teaching methods in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Dimensions of Teachers' Job Effectiveness

Teachers' job effectiveness can be measured using a variety of dimensions. This suggests that teachers' job effectiveness is a multidimensional construct which cut across various instructional related tasks that are assigned to teachers as implementers of the school curriculum. This study is concerned with four imperative dimensions of teachers' job effectiveness; these are lesson planning and delivery, classroom management, students' assessment and feedback, and diversification of teaching methods by teachers. The aforementioned dimensions of teachers' job effectiveness are reviewed below:

Lesson Planning and Instructional Delivery

Lesson planning serves as a fundamental guide for effective classroom instruction, outlining instructional objectives, teaching procedures, learning activities, and evaluation strategies (English Club, 2014). It functions as a structured roadmap that clarifies what students are expected to learn and how learning will be facilitated during instructional time (Milkova, 2021). Effective lesson plans integrate clearly defined learning objectives, appropriate teaching and learning activities, and strategies for assessing students' understanding. Regardless of format, lesson plans are designed to optimise students' learning experiences, ensure instructional consistency, support instructional delivery, and provide a basis for reflection and evaluation of teaching practice (Gagné & Briggs, 1974, cited in University of Wollongong, 2023). Consequently, lesson planning and instructional delivery reflect teachers' ability to design and implement instruction aligned with learning objectives,

utilise diverse instructional strategies, build on students' prior knowledge, and incorporate relevant instructional resources to enhance learning outcomes (University of Florida, 2023).

Classroom Management

Classroom management refers to the systematic organisation and regulation of students, instructional materials, and the learning environment to achieve instructional objectives and enhance students' academic achievement (Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019). It encompasses planning, organising, coordinating, motivating, and controlling classroom activities to facilitate effective instruction (Igbacha, 2014). Effective classroom management involves maintaining discipline, organising learning resources, establishing rules and procedures, and sustaining students' engagement during instruction (Akpakwu, 2012; Brophy, 2016). According to Evertson and Weinstein (2016), classroom management also entails creating a supportive environment that promotes both academic and socio-emotional learning. Teachers' effectiveness is therefore reflected in their ability to prevent disruptive behaviours, foster positive classroom interactions, and provide instructional leadership that ensures a conducive learning environment (Yusuf, 2013).

Students' Assessment and Feedback

Assessment and feedback are integral components of the teaching–learning process and are closely interconnected (Huang, 2015). Feedback plays a critical role in minimising learning gaps, reducing errors, and enhancing students' knowledge and skill acquisition (Tan et al., 2020). Empirical evidence suggests that timely and appropriate feedback significantly improves learning outcomes and academic achievement (Bergil & Atlib, 2012; Panhoon & Wongwanich, 2014). Effective assessment practices enable teachers to evaluate students' learning progress, guide instructional decisions, and improve teaching effectiveness (Aina, Olanipekun, & Garuba, 2015). Assessment activities, including marking, grading, and record keeping, constitute a major aspect of teachers' professional responsibilities and serve as indicators of teachers' job effectiveness within the school system (Ceyhun & Erdogan,

2013). While formative assessment supports and enhances learning, summative assessment focuses on certification, reporting, and progression decisions (Lambert & Lines, 2000, cited in Oduwaiye et al., 2017). Thus, students' assessment and feedback remain central to teachers' instructional and administrative effectiveness in public senior secondary schools.

Teachers' Diversification of Teaching Methods

Teaching methods refer to the strategies and procedures employed by teachers to present subject matter in ways that facilitate learning and achieve instructional objectives (Olowo & Fashiku, 2019). Teaching methods vary in structure and application, reflecting differences in instructional activities and information flow between teachers and students (Afolabi & Adesope, 2010, cited in Olowo & Fashiku, 2019). The effectiveness of instruction largely depends on teachers' ability to select and apply appropriate teaching methods that align with lesson objectives, learner characteristics, and desired learning outcomes (Oke, 2020). Given that no single teaching method is universally effective, teachers are expected to diversify instructional approaches to accommodate learners' differences and enhance students' academic performance. Consequently, the appropriate use of varied teaching methods constitutes a critical dimension of teachers' job effectiveness in the teaching–learning process.

Students' Academic Performance

Students' academic performance is a central goal of secondary education, as outlined in the National Policy on Education, and reflects learners' achievement in internal and external examinations (Narad & Abdullahi, 2016). It is commonly measured through assessments such as class exercises, tests, mid-semester and end-of-semester examinations (Noyelum, Ogugua, & Abah, 2022). Academic performance represents the outcome of education in terms of the extent to which students, teachers, or institutions achieve their educational objectives (Dimkpa, 2015).

Beyond scores, academic performance encompasses knowledge acquisition, skill development, competencies, high grades, and

sustained educational engagement, contributing to career progression and lifelong learning (Kumar, Agarwal, & Agarwal, 2021; Omokhua & Agi, 2021). It also reflects observable behaviours over a defined period, including persistence, progression, and examination results (Yusuf, Onifade, & Bello, 2016; York, Gibson, & Rankin, 2015). Effectively, academic performance is both a quantitative measure of achievement and a qualitative indicator of students’ understanding of curriculum content, critical thinking, and readiness for subsequent learning opportunities (Omokhua & Agi, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this research is anchored on three sets of theories that are related individually to the independent and dependent variables of this study. Thus, theoretically, the study made use of the Teaching Effectiveness Theory by Marzano (2012), and Human Performance Improvement Theory by Mager (1975).

Teacher Job Effectiveness Theory (Marzano, 2012)

Marzano’s (2012) Teacher Job Effectiveness Theory conceptualizes teaching effectiveness as a multidimensional construct, highlighting characteristics of effective teachers and their impact on student outcomes. Teaching effectiveness is measured through goal setting, providing feedback, facilitating interaction with new knowledge, offering simulations and low-stakes competition, enforcing classroom rules, and reteaching when necessary (Marzano, 2012). The theory identifies four domains: pedagogical strategies directly linked to student performance; planning and preparation for units of instruction; teaching with emphasis on evaluation and implementation of academic programs; and

fostering supportive environments that encourage exchange of ideas. Marzano’s theory is relevant to this study as it underscores the role of effective lesson planning, classroom management, diversification of teaching methods, and continuous assessment in promoting students’ academic performance.

Human Performance Improvement Theory (Mager, 1975)

Mager’s (1975) Human Performance Improvement Theory posits three components—performance, conditions, and criterion. Performance defines what the learner should achieve; conditions specify the context under which performance occurs; and criterion establishes the standards for acceptable performance. The theory shifts focus from instructional processes to measurable learner outcomes and emphasizes the importance of clear, explicit, and assessable learning objectives. In the context of secondary education, the theory highlights that students’ academic performance, such as in the WASSCE, reflects both what has been learned and the instructional conditions provided. Adopting Mager’s framework ensures that learning goals are measurable and aligned with assessment standards, guiding teachers in planning and evaluating instructional activities to improve student outcomes. For instance, achieving a minimum of five credit passes including English Language and Mathematics represents the criterion for acceptable performance, illustrating the practical relevance of this theory for improving academic achievement in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 1: Mager’s Theory for Instructional Objective and Performance Problems

Performance	What the learner is able to do.
Conditions	Important conditions under which performance occurs.
Criterion	Quality or level of performance considered acceptable.

Source: Mager (1975)

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted correlational survey and ex-post facto research designs. The correlational survey design was used to establish predictive relationships between teachers’ job effectiveness and students’ academic performance (Filgona & Sakiyo, 2020), while the ex-post facto design enabled the analysis of historical data from students’ SSCE results (2014–2023) without manipulation (Owan, Bassey, & Ekpe, 2020).

Population, Sample, and Sampling Technique

The population comprised 312 public senior secondary schools, 312 principals, and 9,295 teachers across three educational zones in Nasarawa State. A sample of 368 teachers and 62 principals was drawn from 62 schools, representing 20% of the respective populations (Lakens, 2022). Multistage sampling was employed: Nasarawa State was randomly selected from the North Central region; the education zones of Keffi, Lafia, and Akwanga were purposively selected; 62 schools were randomly chosen; principals were randomly selected from each school; and proportional sampling ensured equitable representation across zones.

Research Instruments

Data were collected using the Teachers’ Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ) and the Students’ Academic Performance Proforma (SAPP). The TJEQ is a 24-item, four-point Likert scale measuring four dimensions of job effectiveness: lesson planning and instructional delivery (items 1–6), classroom management (7–12), student assessment and feedback (13–18), and diversification of teaching methods (19–24). Response weights were: Very High Level (4), High Level (3), Moderate Level (2), Low Level (1).

The SAPP collected students’ SSCE results from 2014–2023. Scores were weighted as: five credits including English and Mathematics (4), five credits with English or Mathematics (3), five credits without English/Mathematics (2), less than five credits (1).

Both instruments were face- and content-validated by experts in Test and Measurement and Education Management, University of Abuja. Reliability for the TJEQ was established via a pilot involving four non-participating principals, using split-half and Pearson Product Moment Correlation, yielding a reliability index of 0.71 (Ursachi, Horodnic, & Zait, 2015). The SAPP was not reliability-tested as it consisted of authenticated secondary data.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, percentages) were used to address research questions. Teachers’ job effectiveness scores were interpreted as: 3.25–4.00 (very high), 2.50–3.24 (high), 1.75–2.49 (moderate), 1.00–1.74 (low). Students’ academic performance was classified as: 3.50–4.00 (very good), 2.50–3.49 (good), 1.50–2.49 (poor), 0.00–1.49 (very poor). Inferential analysis was conducted using multiple regression at a 0.05 significance level to test the predictive relationship between teachers’ job effectiveness and students’ academic performance. The null hypothesis was accepted if $p > 0.05$ and rejected if $p < 0.05$.

Data Analysis and Results

What is the level of teachers’ job effectiveness in lesson planning and delivery in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 2: Analysis of Level of Teachers’ Job Effectiveness Public Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria n = 62

S/N	Items: In my school, the teachers	VHL	HL	ML	LL	\bar{x}	S.D	Decision
A	Lesson planning and delivery							High Level
1	adequately prepare for lessons based on subject matter and instructional activities.	22	18	12	10	2.84	.67	High Level
2	take time to re-teach and explain difficult instructional content to students.	21	14	15	12	2.71	.78	High Level

3	effectively present lesson topics related to subject matter.	16	20	12	14	2.61	.84	High Level
4	guide students participation in instructional activities related to subject matter.	22	19	11	10	2.85	.65	High Level
5	engage in interactive exchange of ideas with their students during classroom instruction.	17	21	11	13	2.67	.85	High Level
6	confidently explain difficult subject matter content to facilitate effective learning experiences for students	23	15	10	14	2.76	.74	High Level
	Section Mean/Standard Deviation					2.74	.76	High Level
B	Classroom Management							High Level
7	Keep adequate records of students participation in instructional activities.	21	14	16	11	2.73	.78	High Level
8	Establish clear rules and procedures for students during instructional activities.	17	19	14	12	2.66	.87	High Level
9	Ensures adequate seating arrangement for students in readiness for instruction.	18	18	14	12	2.68	.85	High Level
10	Prioritizes building positive interpersonal relationships with students during the teaching-learning process.	17	21	13	11	2.71	.79	High Level
11	Establish appropriate reward and sanction systems for students.	16	21	13	12	2.66	.86	High Level
12	Enforces order and discipline among students during collaborative instructional activities.	26	14	12	10	2.90	.64	High Level
	Section Mean/Standard Deviation					2.72	.79	High Level
C	Students' Assessment and Feedback							High Level
13	give students assignments and homework regularly.	17	18	13	14	2.61	.85	High Level
14	keep students' academic records for administrative purposes.	20	19	11	12	2.76	.78	High Level
15	conduct continuous assessment to evaluate students' level of learning.	18	16	11	17	2.56	.89	High Level
16	make use of examination to ascertain students' academic improvement.	19	19	10	14	2.70	.79	High Level
17	assign group work to students to encourage team work.	17	19	14	12	2.66	.86	High Level
18	promptly grade of students' performance to provide adequate feedback.	19	17	15	11	2.71	.80	High Level
	Section Mean/Standard Deviation					2.67	.83	High Level
D	Teachers' Use of Teaching Methods							High Level
19	make use of demonstration method in explaining subject matter content to students.	21	14	14	13	2.70	.78	High Level
20	employ collaborate method to ensure students involvement to ensure students involvement in learning activities.	24	13	13	12	2.80	.73	High Level
21	make use of ICT tools in improving the teaching-learning process.	25	15	12	10	2.89	.64	High Level
22	make use of discovery method of instruction to ensure students expand their knowledge base.	23	15	13	11	2.81	.73	High Level
23	make use of project method to develop students' creativity.	22	14	12	14	2.71	.77	High Level
24	make use of questioning method to develop students' attention span and self confidence.	18	18	11	15	2.65	.86	High Level
	Section Mean/Standard Deviation					2.76	.75	High Level
	Overall Mean/Standard Deviation					2.72	.78	High Level

In Table 2, the result of the analysis shows that positive mean values were observed for lesson planning and delivery ($\bar{x} = 2.74$), classroom management ($\bar{x} = 2.72$), students’ assessment and feedback($\bar{x} = 2.67$) and use of teaching

methods ($\bar{x} = 2.76$). The overall section mean of 2.72 which is within the mean values range of 2.50 to 3.24 indicated that there is a high level of teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Key: TTM Teachers’ Use of Teaching Method
 LPD Lesson Planning and Delivery
 CM Classroom Management
 SAF Students’ Assessment and Feedback

Figure 1:Mean Rank Order Distribution of Teachers’ Job Effectiveness Variables in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

The Bar chart in Figure 1 shows the mean rank order distribution of teachers’ job effectiveness variables. Thus, teachers’ use of teaching methods is ranked first (= 2.76), lesson planning and delivery is ranked second (= 2.74), classroom management is ranked third (= 2.72), and students’ assessment and feedback is ranked

fourth (= 2.67) in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two

What is the trend in students’ academic performance in SSCE results in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria from 2014 to 2023?

Table 3: Analysis of Trend of Students’ Academic Performance in SSCE Results in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria from 2014 to 2023

Year	No. of Candidates	4	3	2	1	\bar{x}	S.D	Decision
2014	16,759	4,867	1,619	6,478	3,795	2.45	.94	Poor performance
2015	17,542	5,356	2,993	5,387	3,806	2.56	.83	Good performance
2016	19,879	5,864	4,296	3,915	5,804	2.51	.86	Good performance
2017	21,295	6,753	5,382	4,826	4,334	2.68	.75	Good performance
2018	23,541	7,125	5,603	8,246	2,567	2.73	.72	Good performance
2019	25,673	7,736	6,974	5,886	5,077	2.67	.77	Good performance
2020	27,565	9,654	5,895	5,594	6,422	2.68	.75	Good performance
2021	28,456	11,863	7,176	5,423	3,994	2.95	.68	Good performance
2022	31,347	13,967	6,429	5,962	4,989	2.94	.69	Good performance
2023	34,238	15,759	7,580	6,481	4,418	3.01	.65	Good performance
Total	246,295	88,944	53,947	58,198	45,206	2.72	.76	Good performance
	(100.0%)	(36.1%)	(21.9%)	(23.6%)	(18.4%)			

In Table 3, the result of the analysis shows that a total of 246,295 students sat for the SSCE in the sampled public secondary schools from 2014 to 2023. Out of this number, 88,944 students (36.1%) had 5 credits and above including Mathematics and English Language; 53,947 students (21.9%) had 5 credits with either Mathematics or English Language; while 58,198 students (23.6%) had 5 credits with neither Mathematics nor English Language; while 45,206 students (18.4%) had less than 5 credits or no credit.

In addition, the results show that the highest mean academic performance of 3.01 was recorded in 2023; while the lowest mean academic performance of 2.45 was recorded in 2014. Cumulatively, from 2014 to 2023, the average mean academic performance of students was 2.72. This implies that there was a good performance in the SSCE results from 2014 to 2023 in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, and there were fluctuations in the trend in students' academic performance over the 10 year period.

Key: 2014 (Blue), 2015 (Red), 2016 (Green), 2017 (Purple), 2018 (Orange), 2019 (Brown), 2020 (Dark Blue), 2021 (Olive Green), 2022 (Dark Blue), 2023 (Dark Red)

Figure 2: Mean Score Distribution of Trend in Students' Academic Performance in SSCE Results from 2014 to 2023.

The Bar chart in Figure 2 shows that there was an initial improvement in students' academic performance from 2014 to 2015. This was followed by a decline in the mean academic performance of students from 2.56 to 2.51 from 2015 to 2016. From 2016 to 2018, there was

recovery as performance improved over the 2 years period showing a positive trend ranging from 2.51 to 2.73. From 2018 to 2019, another decline occurred, marking a setback in academic performance. From 2019 to 2021, there was a notable improvement in the academic performance of student ranging from 2.67 to 2.95. From 2021 to 2022, there was a slight drop in performance from 2.95.

Figure 3: Graphical Representation of Trend in Students' Academic Performance in SSCE Results in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria from 2014 to 2023.

The Bar graph in Figure 3 shows that over a 10 year period (2014 to 2023), the trend in students' mean academic performance in the SSCE results is fluctuating with alternating periods of improvement and decline.

Figure 4: Mean Score Distribution of Trend in Students’ Academic Performance in SSCE Results from 2014 to 2023.

The Bar chart in Figure 4 shows that based on the rank order distribution of students’ mean academic performance scores in the SSCE results, the highest mean academic performance score of 3.01 was recorded in 2023, while the lowest mean academic performance score of 2.45 was recorded in 2014.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ job effectiveness and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis of Significant Relationship between Teachers’ Job Effectiveness and Students’ Academic Performance in Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Rank
	B	SE	(B)			
(Constant)	2.675	1.593		2.482	.044	
Lesson planning and Delivery	.172	.047	.281	3.565	.008	2 nd
Classroom Management	.160	.063	.262	3.144	.012	3 rd
Students’ Assessment and Feedback	.147	.075	.230	2.857	.017	4 th
Teachers’ Use of Teaching Methods	.188	.034	.293	3.761	.000	1 st
Dependent Variable: Students’ Academic Performance						

* $p < 0.05$ = Significant relationship

The result of the multiple regression analysis in Table 10 was interpreted using the Beta weight (β), t-values, and p-values of the analysis. According to the result, teachers’ use of teaching methods is the strongest predictor of students’ academic performance ($B=.293$, $t=3.761$, $p=.000 < 0.05$), followed by lesson planning and delivery ($B=.281$, $t=3.565$, $p=.008 < 0.05$), classroom management ($B=.262$, $t=3.144$, $p=.012 < 0.05$), and students’ assessment and feedback ($B=.245$, $t=2.857$, $p=.017 < 0.05$) respectively in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

The p-values of the sub-independent variables were found to be less than the alpha level of 0.05; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between teachers’ job effectiveness and students’ academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed a high level of teachers’ job effectiveness in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. This contrasts with previous findings in other contexts, such as Ondo North Senatorial District (Alabi & Aladetan, 2020), selected North Central states (Amokeye, 2025), and Ondo State (Abdu-Raheem & Bamgbade, 2022), where teacher effectiveness was reported as moderate or low.

Regarding students’ academic performance, the study found a good level of achievement in SSCE results from 2014 to 2023 in Nasarawa State. This aligns with similar observations in North Central Nigeria (Amokeye, 2025) and South-South Nigeria (Aniekop, 2023), indicating a generally positive trend in student outcomes over the period.

Importantly, the study established a significant relationship between teachers’ job effectiveness

and students' academic performance. This finding corroborates prior research demonstrating that teacher effectiveness—encompassing lesson planning, classroom management, instructional methods, and professional ethics—positively influences student achievement (Ahmed, 2016; Adeyemi, 2020; Abdu-Raheem & Bamgbade, 2022; Chikendu, 2022). Comparable results were reported in Malaysia (Kumarasamy & Sundram, 2023) and North-Central Nigeria (Usman & Abubakar, 2020), affirming that teacher competence and management practices are key predictors of student outcomes. These findings suggest that in Nasarawa State, teachers' preparation, instructional strategies, and professional conduct substantially impact students' academic performance, highlighting the critical role of teacher effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes.

Conclusion

The study established that teachers in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State exhibit a high level of job effectiveness, which is reflected in the generally good academic performance of students in SSCE results from 2014 to 2023. The findings further indicate that students' academic achievement is strongly influenced by teachers' effectiveness in key areas such as lesson planning, classroom management, assessment, and the use of diversified teaching methods. In essence, the study confirms that teachers' professional competence and effectiveness serve as significant predictors of students' academic outcomes, underscoring the pivotal role of skilled and dedicated educators in shaping educational success in Nasarawa State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. School principals in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State should provide teaching staff with training opportunities targeted towards further enhancement of their level of effectiveness in lesson planning and delivery, classroom management, students' assessment, and the use of teaching methods.

2. School principals in public senior secondary schools in collaboration with the Nasarawa State Teaching Service Commission should invest in teacher Continuing Professional Development Programmes and provide an enabling support system and environment for teachers to participate actively in CPD activities towards enhancing teachers' effectiveness.
3. School principals should support teachers to focus on students-centered learning approaches that promote active engagement and academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State.

References

- Abdu-Raheem, B. O., & Bamgbade, F. O. (2022). Social studies teachers' effectiveness as an essential factor towards building a new Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies*, 25(1), 1–15.
- Adeyemi, B. A. (2020). Teachers' effectiveness and students' academic achievement in senior secondary school civic, Osun State Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 7(2), 99–103.
- Adzongo, P. I., & Olaitan, T. O. (2019). Effective teaching and classroom management: A tool for quality education in Nigeria. *Benue State University Journal of Education Management*, 1(2), 2–12.
- Ahmed, S. G. (2020). Teaching effectiveness as correlate of academic achievement in senior secondary schools in English Language in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Policy Review*, 12(2), 16–32.
- Aina, J. K., Olanipekun, & Garuba, O. (2015). Assessment practices and instructional effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(6), 6–9.
- Arogundade, B. B., Fakunle, A. F., & Olofin, T. B. (2001). Inspectorate services and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 9(11), 43–53

- Aniekop, I. (2023). Trends in secondary school students' academic performance in South-South Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Innovation, 12(1)*, 45–53.
- Bourn, D., Hunt, F., & Bamber, P. (2017). A review of education for sustainable development and global citizenship education in teacher education. *UNESCO GEM Background Paper. UNESCO*.
- Brohy, R. N. (2016). Classroom management technique. *Education and Urban Education, 5(4)*, 118–127.
- Chikendu, R. E. (2022). Teachers' effectiveness and students' academic performance in secondary schools. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research, 8(2)*, 90–97.
- English Club. (2014). *What is a lesson plan?* <https://www.englishclub.com/esl-lesson-plans/what-is-a-lesson-plan.php>
- Filgona, J., & Sakiyo, J. (2020). Teachers' academic qualification as a predictor of attitude and academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Education Research, 8(3)*, 101–110.
- Igbacha, I. (2014). Classroom management and student learning outcomes. *Journal of Educational Studies, 7(1)*, 12–20.
- Kotherja, S. (2013). Teachers' role in student academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Development, 4(2)*, 23–32.
- Marzano, R. J. (2012). *Teacher effectiveness: A framework for improving classroom practice*. ASCD.
- Milkova, S. (2021). Lesson planning for effective teaching. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research, 20(5)*, 45–60.
- Mager, R. F. (1975). *Preparing instructional objectives*. Fearon Publishers.
- Olowo, T., & Fashiku, C. (2019). Teaching strategies and students' performance in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Learning, 8(4)*, 77–85.
- Osifila, G. I. (2020). Teachers' job effectiveness and students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Research, 9(2)*, 120–129.
- Oviawe, J. I. (2016). Pedagogical competence and teacher effectiveness in secondary schools. *Journal of Research in Education, 8(1)*, 33–40.
- Tan, J., et al. (2020). Feedback in classroom instruction: Effects on student learning. *Journal of Education Research, 13(2)*, 55–66.
- UNESCO. (2018). *Global education monitoring report 2018: Teachers and education quality*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Ursach, G., Horodnic, I.A., & Zait, A. (2015). How reliable are measurement scales? External factors with indirect influence on reliability estimators. *Procedia Economics and Finance, 2(1)*, 676–686
- Usman, A., & Abubakar, H. (2020). Teacher competence and student performance in North-Central Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Education, 12(3)*, 56–65.
- Yusuf, M. O., Onifade, O., & Bello, A. (2016). Academic performance and teacher effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Development, 10(1)*, 23–32.
- York, T., Gibson, C., & Rankin, S. (2015). Student achievement and instructional quality: Evidence from secondary schools. *Journal of Education Studies, 7(4)*, 99–111.